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Description (short)
Interoperable and shared European digital research infrastructures (DRI) shall enable ENLIGHT researchers to better collaborate, share their research data, and develop new ideas. Connecting DRIs is a complex process for all actors involved. This report brings together examples of current work tasks and challenges, using examples from DARIAH, CLARIN, NBIS (the Swedish node in ELIXIR). The goal is to provide insights into the diversity of the task related to connecting DRIs.

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Executive Summary

FAIRification of research data and connecting digital research infrastructures (DRIs) in order to explore new possibilities in research, innovation and AI are strategic goals for Digital Europe. This report illustrates the complexity of the challenges encountered in the process of connecting local or national DRIs with European infrastructures to achieve interoperability between services, resources and research tools. Balancing the functional requirements of DRIs while enriching them with domain-specific content is an important task. The integration at the European level adds complexity, necessitating a clear understanding of the added value it should generate. Associated processes involve questions regarding goals and priorities, cultural and organizational differences, governance and decision making, and intellectual property. At the same time, human resources with respect to workload, time, and creativity also play a role in the process of connecting DRI. To give insights into the diversity of the tasks, this report brings together examples from DARIAH, CLARIN, and NBIS (the Swedish node in ELIXIR).

Abbreviations

ENLIGHT Partner	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
National University of Ireland, Galway	NUIG	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

AAI: Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

CESSDA: Consortium of European Social Science Data Archive

CLARIN: Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure

DARIAH: Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities

DRI: Digital Research Infrastructure

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud

ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable

IF: Interoperability Framework

INTELE: INfraestructura de TEcnologías del LEnguaje

NBIS: National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden

OA: Open Access

OS: Open Science

RI: Research Infrastructure

SSH: Social Sciences and Humanities

SSHOC: Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

TRL: technical readiness level

Introduction

Interoperable and shared European digital research infrastructures (DRI) provide an environment that enables ENLIGHT researchers to enhance their collaborative work and to exchange their research data. A coherent and interconnected system that supports research activities across multiple disciplines, institutions, and geographic locations is the result of successful integration of RIs. Integration means to combine various research tools, resources, and services to create a system that supports scientific work and innovation. Research infrastructures include all of the physical and digital resources that researchers use to conduct their work, such as laboratory facilities, equipment, databases, software tools, and communication networks.¹ Domain specific local or national DRIs and cross-domain work can benefit from the connection with well-organized research infrastructures on a European level. Integrating infrastructures on the European level (e.g. via an ESFRI Research Infrastructure² or other relevant initiatives) aims at increasing the individual and collective benefits of interoperability, e.g. the sharing of infrastructures can ease the individual workload, reduce costs, and it can also assist in generating new research ideas in the collaboration process. Ideally, a full integration takes place at the technical, institutional-organizational, and legal level, for example, when a national DRI and its services are integrated into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which makes them “the provider” in this process. Depending on the complexity of the national research infrastructure, this consists of many steps, each with its specific requirements. The host provider (in this case EOSC) must also offer the right structures for the integration. The technical and legal prerequisites for integration need to be verified on both sides in order to decide which service can be integrated when and to which extent. The first time these prerequisites are checked is during the so-called onboarding process into the EOSC portal: “The EOSC Portal Onboarding Process is the process that an EOSC provider must follow to register the provider and its Resources in the EOSC Portal Registry.”³ Onboarding is

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures_en

² <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/>

³ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Portal+Onboarding+Process>.

a registration process that is formally adding service(s) to the EOSC catalogue. The services are added “on the EU map of available resources”⁴, which means they are visible in the EOSC marketplace. “Onboarding your service, in the current architecture of the EOSC, means populating the EOSC-Exchange layer”⁵.

However, onboarding is not “integrating”, as colleagues who are involved in the integration process of providers’ resources into the EOSC as well as the interviewees of these case studies explained.⁶ It rather is the first step towards integration. Only the technical integration of data or services can guarantee the interoperability researchers are looking for. Incomplete integration may result in errors, bugs or inaccessibility of resources or services when accessing them via the EOSC portal, even if they are still fully functional and available on the providers’ side.

The connection with and integration into European infrastructures should not only provide the users with general access to already established and well-developed local national services, but it should also create added values and improvements for them as well as for the providers. These values could be new services that so far did not exist. The value of expanding access to services or service-bundles that are part of other institutions and are easily findable and accessible via the platform of the shared European infrastructure is attractive for researchers and providers.

In order to learn more about the challenges of the integration processes and the topics that need to be considered in this context, semi-structured interviews were conducted with Sally Chambers and Nanette Reißler-Pipka for DARIAH (UGENT, UGOE); Mikel Iruskieta for CLARIN (UPV/EHU); Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström and Niclas Jareborg for the Swedish ELIXIR-node NBIS (UU).

All interviewees are involved in integration processes in different ways and they provide insights into various aspects that all have to be considered and dealt with when connecting infrastructures. It is well known that the realization of visions requires a lot of work and time. Connecting infrastructures comes with several challenges and difficulties, unforeseen obstacles can change or slow down the whole processes. Planned (technical) integrations may not take place the way they were anticipated. Often, support or solutions are not immediately available or have not been developed yet. This report gives an impression of the time-consuming workload, and the manifold challenges of various tasks that develop when connecting DRIs.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/1060>.

⁶ Informal talks during work related meetings with people of EOCS WP5 in February 2023, and case study interviews December 2022, January and February 2023.

Method

To gain in-depths insights into the efforts, challenges and tasks that are needed to integrate disciplinary DRIs with the EOSC, three examples with involvement of ENLIGHT partners were selected. Information on the connecting and integration processes was collected by interviewing persons who are actively involved in these tasks at different interfaces and who agreed on sharing their information and knowledge. Interviewees were identified through joint work in ongoing projects and through personal contacts in ENLIGHT RISE work packages. The methodological process consisted of the following steps:

1. Semi-structured interviews: The interviews were conducted via web conference and recorded. A few predetermined questions were asked while the rest of the questions emerged spontaneously in the conversations.
2. In addition to the interviews sources like publications, websites and workflow data sheets provided during the interviews were reviewed. The [ENLIGHT Workshop#2](#) on *Connecting Digital Research Infrastructures with European Infrastructures - Experiences and Lessons Learned* (March 15, 2023)⁷ provided additional insights into the topic. The aim of considering these additional sources was to obtain a so-called orientation knowledge and to identify first specificities. Some of the secondary sources were internal workflow documents that were shared by the interviewees for a deeper understanding and, therefore, are not added in the appendix of this report.
3. All interviews were transcribed automatically with the program "AIKO" and then analyzed regarding their main topics and key terms. This revealed a set of similar topics that were part of each case study. There were, however, different challenges in the respective working tasks, depending on technology readiness level (TRL), level of integration, legal conditions, but also workload, time pressure and other issues.
4. A more detailed qualitative data analysis followed, using the software [MAXQDA](#): The transcriptions were imported into the software for analysis. A set of categories was defined based on topics and terms that frequently appeared. These categories were saved as so-called codes in the project, all in all 41 different codes. Table 1 represents the codes sorted by their frequency to illustrate which topics were addressed with what frequency.
5. The coding of the qualitative data (categorizing interview): The predefined codes were assigned to the respective segments of the interviews. Some new codes were additionally defined during coding. Some of the interviews were quite long and the transcripts consist of a large amount of data. Here the MAXQDA "Search and Autocode tool" allowed to search the entire material or a part thereof for specific terms and automatically coded the

⁷ ENLIGHT RISE webinar on Digital infrastructure: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AAV39bK3Fw4>

search hits. Even though the process of defining codes is very time consuming, the automatic application saved a lot of time. Still the transcript had to be read again carefully to check if all codes had been applied correctly.

6. Not all text segments could be coded automatically, because they describe general thoughts, tendencies or activities. Therefore, additional codes such as “future”, “criticism” or “solution” were included in the code system. The coding of these segments did not take place automatically, but this had to be done manually based on close reading of the transcript.
7. After the coding, an in-depth analysis of topics coded in the interviews was undertaken. The software allowed to compile all text segments that were coded with one (or more) codes which facilitated the comparison of topics and their contexts.
8. The comparisons and the analysis of the coding and key terms allowed a description of task- examples of each case study, of challenges that were faced and of ideas and thoughts related to current developments. Each case study starts with a short overview of key tasks and key challenges related to different topics discussed in the interviews. Then descriptions of topics addressed in the interviews were compiled.
9. The last chapter summarizes general challenges based on the overall findings, additionally key aspects such as workload, time and creativity are also taken into account.

Table 1: Codes System, Selection Sorted by Frequency⁸

Code	Frequency (all interviews)
service	410
data	287
infrastructure	244
researcher and research	198
EOSC	191
integration	134
resource	132
core service	131
provider	115
onboarding	104
interoperability	103
science	94
user, mindset change	90

⁸ This is a selection of the most common codes, for the complete table see the appendix.

The Case Studies

DARIAH

Background

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) aims to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices and sustains researchers in using them to build, analyze and interpret digital resources.⁹ DARIAH integrates digital arts and humanities research and activities from across Europe, enabling transnational and transdisciplinary approaches. The activities are based on four strategic pillars: 1. Digital platform: building a central digital platform to facilitate researchers' access to specific tools, services and research data; 2. Education: creation of education and training opportunities via traditional or online training programmes; 3. Science policy: spokesperson for researchers and stakeholders at the European level (e.g. in the area of "Open Science"); 4. Innovation: coordination of currently about twenty transnational and interdisciplinary working groups dealing with new, innovative research topics.¹⁰

DARIAH also engages in activities and projects that aim at improving the collaboration and communication among the five SSH ERICs (CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS, SHARE, CESSDA) to create synergies and benefit from their respective strengths (e.g. via the cluster project Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC), 2019-2022).

Two separated interviews were conducted with a) Sally Chambers, Digital Humanities Research Coordinator at the Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities and coordinator of Belgian participation in DARIAH, and with b) Nanette Reißler-Pipka, co-managing director of DARIAH-DE and National Coordinator of Germany for DARIAH ERIC.

The interview with Chambers focused on different examples to offer insights into the complex tasks and structures related to the onboarding and integration workflows. Depending on the size of a service and the desired functions in EOSC (i.e., integration into core services), the integration processes vary significantly.

The conversation with Reißler-Pipka focused primarily on integration challenges regarding the EOSC core services. The EOSC core services include a technical platform (AAI, Monitoring, Helpdesk, Marketplace) and non-technical functions (Onboarding, Order Management, Open Science Support), it promotes Open Science, interdisciplinary collaboration, and shall maximize research value. Integration with the core services is related to several processes and decisions and the aim is to create an infrastructure that is designed to best fit the users' needs.

⁹ <https://www.dariah.eu/about/dariah-in-nutshell/>.

¹⁰ <https://cmb.hu-berlin.de/forschung/digital-humanities/dariah>.

For better orientation, the following bullet points briefly summarize tasks and challenges that were mentioned in the interview. They are subsequently presented in more detail in the sections below.

Overview Key Tasks

- Onboarding providers and their resources into the EOSC portal registry
- Integration with EOSC core services
- Integrating research infrastructures and services from different science clusters¹¹ into EOSC
- Ensuring seamless functionality and integration between EOSC and provider repositories
- Handling and integrating huge infrastructure landscapes with large amounts of data
- Establishing well-functioning interfaces between EOSC and providers' service catalogues
- Enhancing user experience in the EOSC Marketplace, including addressing login issues and communicating service availability

Overview Key Challenges

- Selecting and prioritizing services for onboarding based on their maturity and integration potential, addressing the technical readiness and development stages of core services
- Coordinating and aligning onboarding and integration efforts between different levels and clusters, and their diverse policies, practices, and priorities
- Achieving full functional integration with research catalogues, establishing interfaces
- Close collaboration between service providers and core service providers
- Handling large-scale infrastructure landscapes with extensive data sources
- Ensuring effective helpdesk integration and support mechanisms
- Optimizing workflows and minimizing dependence on specific individuals in order to create an efficient and reliable system

Examples of Responsibilities and Challenges

Cooperation, Coordination and Alignment

The process of connecting infrastructures is influenced by various factors at different levels, including the institutional, research infrastructure, national, and European levels. The

¹¹ https://www.panosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/2021-06-17-EOSC_Symposium-SCs.pdf

interconnections between these levels, as well as the diverse policies within countries and institutions, significantly impact the process of integrating infrastructures.

At the institutional level, each organisation has its own set of policies, practices and priorities. These factors can shape the approach to infrastructure integration and determine the level of cooperation and compatibility between different institutions.

Similarly, research infrastructures operate with their own unique requirements, objectives, and collaborations. Their specific needs and capabilities play a crucial role in determining how infrastructures can be connected and integrated effectively.

On a national level, differences in policies, regulations, and funding mechanisms across countries can pose challenges to infrastructure integration. A service provider for example in Sweden may have specific policies that encourage data sharing and open access to research outputs, whereas another service provider for example in Germany with whom they would like to connect services might have more restrictive policies in place. An institute in a certain country might have stringent regulations related to data protection and privacy, than another institute. These variations must be taken into account to ensure that the integration efforts align with national strategies and adhere to relevant regulations.

At the European level, there are broader frameworks and initiatives aimed at coordinating and facilitating infrastructure integration across borders. These initiatives, such as EOSC, provide guidelines, standards, and funding opportunities to support the harmonisation and collaboration of research infrastructures at a European scale. However, research does not stop at European borders, so both research infrastructures and EOSC needs to be considered in a global context.

Considering all these factors, including the interconnections and policy disparities, is essential for successfully connecting infrastructures. It requires coordination, cooperation, and alignment of policies and practices at various levels to ensure a seamless and efficient integration process.

Disciplines and Marketplaces

One of the objectives of EOSC is to ensure the representation of all disciplines, which can be achieved by looking at the science clusters. Each science cluster¹² brings together several disciplinary research infrastructures, resulting in different technical and content requirements. Chambers explains that, for instance, the SSHOC cluster has its own catalogue called the SSH Open Marketplace¹³. Within the SSHOC cluster alone, there are multiple research infrastructures, each with its own portfolio of services and data sources as well. The goal is to

¹² <https://science-clusters.eu>

¹³ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu>

bring as many resources as possible into EOSC and enhance diversity. Consequently, providers need to decide what should be onboarded into EOSC. An interesting aspect to consider is the interrelationship between the SSH Open Marketplace and EOSC. Would a domain researcher be more inclined to visit the SSH Open Marketplace, due to research habits, or access the services rather via the EOSC marketplace? Furthermore, what is the connection between the two platforms?

“If we compare it to the SSH Open Marketplace, the EOSC marketplace is something similar: there are tools and services, training materials, publications and data. There are over 6,400 resources in the SSH Open Marketplace. And here the terminology becomes quite complex when we talk about integration. So what we meant by integrating is the core services. Currently we work with six EOSC core services”, Chambers said.

Those six core services are: 1. accounting for research products, 2. accounting for services, 3. monitoring, 4. helpdesk, 5. EOSC AAI and 6. order management.

She went on explaining that there are certain research services that have a high potential for integration, meaning they are considered important by specific research infrastructures and should be visible in EOSC. These services may be interested in integrating with multiple core services. To ensure representation from all five clusters, there should be core service integrations that cover each cluster. This means that different types of services from each science cluster will be integrated with different core services.

“In the case of DARIAH, which has around 200 services, not all of them are mature enough to be onboarded into EOSC. However, in the medium-term, it will be possible to exchange resources between the SSH Open Marketplace and EOSC, including the indexing of the most mature services and data sources from SSHOC into EOSC. Additionally, each research infrastructure aims to prioritise the best interests of its own users”, Chambers explained.

Regarding service portfolio management, there is a question of whether all research products within a specific service (e.g. datasets within a research data repository) should be indexed into EOSC and she mentioned a selection process that is needed:

“In some of the larger clusters, there are hundreds of services, but we will not have the time to do all these integrations. We therefore had to choose selectively and how we did it was quite pragmatically in the beginning, by looking at which services are already onboarded. If somebody has onboarded them, they must have thought that these services had integration potential. Integration is a social as well as a technical process.”

Another observation shared during the interviews was that users of the EOSC Marketplace are expressing disappointment due to login pages they reach after having clicked on “Go to

Service” or “Go to Tool” for their desired services. This necessitates the establishment of criteria to ensure that the services provided are accessible. The core service “Order Management” in EOSC plays a crucial role, allowing users to indicate whether a service is available or specify the number of computing facilities available. It is essential to effectively communicate this information to users, as their experiences will ultimately determine the success of the platform. If users encounter disappointment, they are unlikely to continue utilizing the platform.

Within the science cluster SSHOC, there is already the aforementioned SSH Open Marketplace, which prompts the question of the added value of the EOSC Marketplace. The argument here is that users from different disciplines can potentially discover services and tools via EOSC that they may not have encountered otherwise. Moreover, they can also connect and collaborate with other projects¹⁴ within the network.

Furthermore, users seek to leverage synergies through the EOSC platform. The “project idea feature”¹⁵ in the Marketplace enables the assembly of project-relevant elements. However, if users already know what they need, there may be no reason to visit the EOSC Marketplace, as they can directly access the service or approach the service provider. Although the intention is for users to be inspired and generate new ideas through projects, the technical process is not advanced enough yet to facilitate this. The desire to collect everything, including the complete content of the providers’ catalogues, can lead to chaos that can only be partially mitigated through search functionalities.

Onboarding Processes

Onboarding is the process that an EOSC provider must follow to register the provider and its resources in the EOSC Portal Registry. Once onboarded the provider is visible in the marketplace. Regarding the onboarding, there are strict guidelines from EOSC, and providers need to check the Technology Readiness Level (TRL)¹⁶ of their services, to see if they have reached the TRL. But there are other prerequisites needed:

“You also need to be clear in your consortium about which services you want to select. DARIAH has put a lot of effort into this, for example in the National Coordinators Committee, in which the coordinators from the member countries of the individual DARIAH national nodes meet on a regular basis”, Rißler-Pipka said.

¹⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc-projects>

¹⁵ https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/about_projects

¹⁶ EOSC requirements of technical readiness level describe in the EOSC Future Glossary, entry "TRL".
<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Future+Glossary>

Each consortium has pursued different onboarding strategies. Consequently, the EOSC catalogue is not stringent and the current EOSC catalogue for the humanities is quite limited. Rißler-Pipka suggests:

“This could be regulated by a policy, but so far there are many requirements in the onboarding process. With regards to the TRL, one difficulty is that it is not checked whether the high-end level specifications 7, 8 or 9 are applicable: it can simply be claimed.”

Ultimately, it is an individual decision and the respective institution responsible for providing the information on the TRL needs to have a functional email address. Responsible persons and prerequisites that guarantee a technical standard are a necessary condition:

“DARIAH is a consortium of several partners and the individual partners run the services. For example, the GWDG¹⁷ operates many services together with the State and University Library Göttingen. And then you have to appoint a responsible person. Notable repositories such as TextGrid¹⁸ or DARIAH-DE Repository are relevant, TextGrid is currently in the onboarding process. These repositories have obtained a CoreTrustSeal¹⁹ certification, indicating their compliance with the Trusted Digital Repository standards.”

As part of the onboarding process, Rißler-Pipka explains that the repositories must provide detailed descriptions of their technical infrastructure, including disaster recovery, backup systems, and IT security measures. These descriptions undergo thorough scrutiny as part of the certification evaluation. There are explanatory videos available to guide the onboarding process, ensuring that all necessary requirements are met:

“Initially, onboarding was limited to personal contacts, but now it has been fully optimized. A provider is required to gather comprehensive information about their institution, the services they offer, and their infrastructure. Upon successful onboarding, an account is created in the provider portal, granting access to information about the core services.”

Providers are automatically enrolled in the core service monitoring – which is a basic monitoring that only checks the functionality of the given link delivered by the provider, and it does not monitor the actual services offered by the provider. As Rißler-Pipka clarifies, “this is a basic monitoring process to ensure that the link functions properly.”

¹⁷ Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung, <https://gwdg.de/en/>

¹⁸ <https://textgrid.de/en/>

¹⁹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org>

Integration with the Core Services

The EOSC Future core platform federates existing and new infrastructures into a system of systems.²⁰ The EOSC core services are currently at various stages of development, and not all of them have completed their technical readiness. At this time, this presents a significant challenge and Rišler-Pipka describes:

“The core services needed to be prepared technically first, and now the focus is on gathering the necessary information and optimizing workflows. An example for this is the ENVRI Fair Science Cluster, which recently invested substantial effort into creating a comprehensive spreadsheet listing all the services they offer.²¹ Providers were then approached to gauge their interest in the core services. However, many providers responded with ‘maybe’ because they were unsure about the actual implications and benefits of the core services.”

If a provider already offers a more advanced core service, for example monitoring, they do not need to utilize the one provided by EOSC, as it would result in redundant monitoring. The attractiveness of the Core services lies in their appeal to those who do not already possess them, considering that hardly any provider offers all core services.

The mission of CESSDA, to look at another example which Chambers was using, is to serve as the consortium of social science data archives in Europe. The CESSDA data catalogue is a compilation of national data catalogues, and one of CESSDA’s key services, and from the outset was a priority for integration into EOSC. The decision to integrate is made by CESSDA’s management, while the integration process is handled by the technical team. Currently, CESSDA has four services²² that have been onboarded into EOSC. They have integrated their data catalogue, which includes data from each of their national nodes, into EOSC. As part of their integration strategy, CESSDA’s management has decided to utilize the EOSC help desk for all their services.

In addition to the core services, the integration of entire research outputs/products catalogues proves to be interesting. For instance, if the information from an entire repository or catalogue needs to be incorporated, an interface between EOSC and the provider’s own repository must be established. The objective is to always ensure seamless functionality between the two platforms.

²⁰ Overview EOSC core: <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/EOSC-Core.pdf>

²¹ <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>

²² [https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/search/service?q=*&fq=resource_organisation:\(%22Consortium%20of%20European%20Social%20Science%20Data%20Archives%20ERIC%22\)](https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/search/service?q=*&fq=resource_organisation:(%22Consortium%20of%20European%20Social%20Science%20Data%20Archives%20ERIC%22))

The Integration Fact Sheets²³ available in the Public Wiki of EOSC for the core services offer descriptions of integration options, including the Helpdesk. Three integration paths are outlined:

a) Full integration: This entails complete synchronization between the EOSC Helpdesk and the community helpdesk. Achieving this integration involves the implementation of a set of helpdesk REST APIs.

b) Ticket redirection: In this integration approach, the EOSC helpdesk serves as a contact point to redirect initial requests to the provider's or community's mailing list without further integration.

c) Direct usage: This integration option allows the EOSC helpdesk to be used as the ticketing system for the community and their onboarded services. However, on the above-mentioned integration fact sheet page it is not clearly described how the integration works in terms of technical implementation, but rather what the goal is. For more specific questions one needs to contact the support.

Integration with core services is a step-by-step process, the infrastructures need to determine which core service, if any, is useful, taking into account their own goals, workload and user needs. To better understand what needs to be considered for connecting and integrating processes, one needs to look at both the providers' details and the overall structural complexity at the same time. Tasks from both sides shape the connecting-challenge.

Core service AAI

EOSC AAI (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure) allows users to log into services using their institutional accounts or popular platforms like Google or Facebook, based on the provider's preferences. While it is not considered a direct core service, it functions as a layer in front of the core services.

The EU-funded H2020 project EOSC Future, that is implementing the European Open Science Cloud,²⁴ actively promotes the core services and encourages exploration. Many individuals and organizations anticipate these services, especially if they lack their own AAI solution or helpdesk, and would benefit from utilizing them. Numerous projects within EOSC are already familiar with the core services and have worked with them in the past. For those without these services in their portfolio, the core services offer a valuable opportunity to fulfill their needs through EOSC.

²³ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Helpdesk+-+integration+factsheet>

²⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/about/>

Core Service Monitoring

Providers who are part of a European consortium and collaborate with partners in other countries may not automatically have access to the core services, Rißler-Pipka explains. In case of system overload, it is crucial for the community to identify the underlying issue. The basic monitoring included in the onboarding process is insufficient for this purpose. Therefore, integrating monitoring capabilities and a helpdesk service becomes crucial. When selecting a core service, factors such as the size of the institution behind the service, the availability of similar services, and the potential benefits for the provider should be considered to enhance professionalism.

Rißler-Pipka recounts an instance in which setting up a video conference was necessary between EOSC's onboarding team, the monitoring team, and the person responsible for onboarding the service for the entire consortium. This communication loop alone consumed a month of work, all for a simple check mark in the provider's portal. The reasons for duplicating the check mark requirement in the onboarding process for the core services can be understood from the technical perspective, still, it is a lot of time that is used for these processes alone.

The current workflow poses challenges due to the large number of providers and their numerous requests. These obstacles need to be addressed and made more visible. Optimizing workflows still heavily relies on individuals, and emails often end up in poorly maintained accounts, leading to delays in forwarding or processing. The objective is to minimize dependence on individuals and create a system that operates efficiently without relying on specific individuals.

Core Service Helpdesk

When an important tool is developed for the community within an institute and managed by a small team, typically consisting of very few individuals, even in large repositories, it can create challenges. One significant issue arises when there is no dedicated helpdesk and only a personal email address is provided as the contact point. Rißler-Pipka explains that this becomes problematic when the person responsible for the tool leaves the project or institution, as there is no established mechanism to address inquiries or support requests. Consequently, the absence of proper infrastructure-management undermines professionalism. Instead, the developers often need to resort to contacting individuals directly via the provided email addresses, bypassing the intended support mechanisms. The complexity of integration varies depending on the specific usage scenario. For example, redirecting tickets to the helpdesk is simpler for a single service compared to registering an entire consortium. Additionally, the integration should not introduce new barriers, such as

restricted access, that were not present before. Therefore, comprehensive testing is necessary to ensure a smooth integration process.

Handling huge infrastructure landscapes is another challenge to be considered. Zenodo as one example, is indexed regularly through the EOSC. So, there is already a critical mass of data:

“We want to get as many services, data sources, etc. onboarded and integrated into EOSC. We talk here about 60 research infrastructures across the five clusters... the research infrastructure landscape is huge”, Chambers explained.²⁵

The SeaDataNet Common Data Index (CDI)²⁶, another example referred to by Chambers, is part of the ENVRI-FAIR²⁷ cluster of environmental research infrastructures and manages several million data records. The data source is growing substantially every day. It therefore must be decided whether it is useful to index all these records via EOSC as well, or to just make some of the aggregated data available.

OS as Opportunity

EOSC is a human and social as well as a technical infrastructure, as Chambers reflected. The onboarding and integration process helps service providers to decide what kinds of integration are available and feasible. Additionally, there is a dedicated category of services called “Horizontal Services”²⁸ which can serve general types of EOSC consumers and may be used by EOSC providers to enrich their services with new capabilities. Services served by computing centres and e-Infrastructures such as computing power, storage and analysis tools, such as Jupyter notebooks are recognised as Horizontal Services. Those services are intended to encourage new research ideas because there is the increasing potential to see what is possible with your data, especially from a cross-disciplinary perspective. The EOSC Future project is developing a number of showcase integration stories to demonstrate the potential of EOSC for researchers from a range of disciplines. Chambers points out that successful integration processes need time:

“EOSC is a really big investment in changing science culture, in technical change and also in collaboration with researchers of different disciplines who inform us about their needs at the same time. It is not going to happen overnight. At the same time, we need to manage expectations as well. The idea is to bring the research infrastructures together and help them to provide their services, tools and data to EOSC. And this is a complex undertaking”.

²⁵ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/explore-the-map/>

²⁶ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/CDI-Common-Data-Index>

²⁷ <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>

²⁸ <https://handbook.eosc-synergy.eu/eosc-architecture/>

In terms of open access, Rißler-Pipka describes that it is important to emphasize that using and reusing research data, scientific publishing and access services should be free from restrictions and payment. The necessary structures and access points are already established, so joining the EOSC in this context is not a mandatory requirement for achieving open access but something that could additionally increase visibility. However, it is crucial to share information about alternative cross-disciplinary publication options for each subject area. She stresses that it is worth noting that an increasing number of open access journals are emerging within various communities, particularly in the humanities. This means that researchers no longer need to publish in restricted access. Sharing such information is relatively inexpensive and can be a renewed focus, especially within a network like ENLIGHT.

CLARIN

Background

The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) is a digital infrastructure with participating data centres all over Europe and further afield, which include universities, research centres, libraries and public archives. CLARIN provides easy and sustainable access to a broad range of language data and tools to support research in the humanities and social sciences, and beyond. The tools and data from the different centres are interoperable so that data collections can be combined and tools from different sources can be chained to perform operations at different levels of complexity, regardless of their location. The interoperability of data and services across the CLARIN community has enabled large-scale data sharing and growing reuse of language resources. In addition, interoperability has also proven crucial for the increased support of multidisciplinary collaboration and comparative research agendas. The vision of borderless and seamless interoperability between data and services is further realized through CLARIN's alignment with emerging platforms such as the EOSC.²⁹

The interview was conducted with Mikel Irukieta, computational linguist, part of the Ixa Research Group and the Didactics of Language and Literature Department at the University of the Basque country and Member of the Knowledge Sharing Infrastructure Committee (CLARIN-ERIC).

For better orientation, the following bullet points briefly summarize tasks and challenges that were mentioned in the interview. They are subsequently presented in more detail in the sections below.

²⁹ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/about-clarin>

Overview Key Tasks

- Building an infrastructure for language and humanities research within Spain, involving different regions, disciplines and languages
- Establishing connections and collaboration with European infrastructures like CLARIN and DARIAH
- Developing user-friendly tools and services that meet the specific needs of researchers
- Promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and shaping the future direction of the field
- Encouraging more institutions and researchers in Spain to join and contribute to research initiatives within Europe

Overview Key Challenges

- Overcoming scepticism about the role of technology in linguistics and humanities research
- Addressing financial constraints and navigating the complexity of Spain's political and linguistic landscape
- Establishing and interconnecting infrastructures across diverse organizations, countries, and languages
- Balancing researchers' requirements and expectations with long-term planning
- Transforming institutional working cultures to accept a multilingual perspective and also European international collaboration

Examples of Responsibilities and Challenges

The interview shed light on the journey undertaken by researchers and institutions to acknowledge the importance of technology in language and humanities research. Overcoming initial skepticism and advocating for the inclusion of Spain in European DRIs required dedication, persistence, and persuasive efforts. According to IruSKIETA, this process spanned a period of about 13 years.

One of the major challenges encountered was initial skepticism regarding the role of technology in linguistics, financial problems, the complexity of Spain's political and linguistic landscape, and at the same time the need to build an infrastructure while involving researchers from various disciplines and regions. Back in 2009, there was a prevailing belief that research in these fields primarily involved traditional methods like pen and paper and extensive library research. Overcoming this mindset was a crucial step in embracing the potential of technology.

Both, CLARIN and DARIAH are important infrastructures for language and humanities research. CLARIN provides access to diverse linguistic data, corpora, software and tools, enabling

researchers to conduct multilingual studies and facilitating collaboration among European countries. DARIAH, on the other hand, focuses on advancing digital methods, tools, and resources in the arts and humanities, fostering interdisciplinary research and facilitating access to digital collections.

The Road to Joining an Infrastructure

Iruskieta explains, that previous attempts to join DARIAH had failed. The formation of INfraestructura de TEcnologías del LEnguaje (INTELE)³⁰, a strategic network, brought together the Spanish National Library and research groups with the aim to create an infrastructure for humanities and language studies. A manifesto signed by nearly 760 researchers showcased their interest in collaborating with CLARIN and DARIAH. This paved the way for Spain's engagement with these infrastructures, marking a significant milestone in the country's involvement in European research initiatives.

But connecting infrastructures relies on the prerequisite of building them first. Iruskieta explains that CLARIN is organized over several countries in Europe, but each country has its own infrastructure and has its own offices. The situation in Spain presents significant challenges due to its diverse linguistic landscape, as well as the presence of multiple political and economic organizations. There is a strong wish to establish an interesting infrastructure that facilitates open science, fosters integration of tools, and is user-friendly.

Creating a Smaller Europe within Spain

Iruskieta describes that to build the infrastructure it is necessary to work in two ways: first to build the infrastructure within Spain, in the Basque country, in Galicia, and Catalonia, and second to cooperate with the European infrastructure:

“We cannot build the infrastructure without the knowledge of our researchers; we want to build this infrastructure with the cooperation of all the meaningful actors. CLARIN as an infrastructure ‘is ready’, but for Basque language you don't have so many projects or services, there is only the general service. We have different research groups and their tools are not in CLARIN, so we need to add all of that.”

Additionally, the tools themselves need to be better developed for easy access, “there are researchers who want to work with the Basque language but they don't have the knowledge of the tools or services”. When universities and institutes from various regions express interest in becoming part of CLARIN, one carefully needs to consider which different infrastructures are needed to support this goal. Simultaneously, these infrastructures need to be interconnected, encompassing numerous organizations, countries, and languages.

³⁰ <https://ixa2.si.ehu.eus/intele/manifiesto>

“It is like creating a smaller Europe within Spain. The challenge lies in deciding which disciplines should be associated with each infrastructure and subsequently constructing the functions within each infrastructure. Complications arise due to variations in planning, diverse stakeholders, and distinct roles across different infrastructures. The task at hand involves defining all these aspects to facilitate connection and integration”, Iruskieta explains.

Time and Expectation

Spain aims to build an infrastructure in collaboration with European partners, both at a national level and within specific regions such as the Basque Country, Galicia and Catalonia. Therefore, there is a need for interoperability, user-friendly tools, and greater participation from researchers in diverse disciplines. But researchers find it challenging to envision the future and plan their work beyond the next couple of years. While it may be easier to predict research activities in the short term, looking further into the future poses difficulties. Iruskieta emphasizes the importance of considering future needs and developments in order to build new programs, projects, and services within the infrastructure. He suggests that researchers should actively engage in discussions, think critically about existing tools and services, and explore interdisciplinary collaborations to shape the future direction of the field.

CLARIN provides a wide range of services and tools, yet there is room for improvement in effectively communicating how these resources can address research questions:

“We are starting and we need people from other disciplines to join in the discussions so that we can learn if and how the tools are working and what the difficulties and specific needs are.”

The open science agenda generates significant interest, and researchers recognize its potential benefits. However, it may not always align with researchers’ specific requirements, and the immediate benefits might not be readily apparent to them: “It is not easy, because at the same time we have to collaborate with the researchers. It is very complicated”. As an infrastructure, decisions regarding the inclusion or exclusion of certain services do not always fully meet the expectations of all researchers in the end.

“We have a plan what we want to do in the next five years with concrete steps for each year regarding the services for CLARIN and DARIAH. We need to update all that and it must be linked to the CLARIN Europe infrastructure. Additionally, we need to create services and tools that we don't have in the Basque country. And based on this, we want to make them available for CLARIN and DARIAH in other European countries – and we want to collaborate with partners, institutions and researchers for Basque language. So, this is how we are constructing the connections - step by step.”

Inspiring Examples and Work Practices

Iruskieta introduced in the interview the ParlaMint project³¹ that serves as an exemplary model in its approach towards multilingualism:

“I think ParlaMint is the first project that was multilingual right from the beginning, and not multilingual only at the end. The project’s emphasis on metadata and thoughtful considerations allowed the construction of a truly multilingual corpus, thereby enabling its meaningful utilization in the fields of social sciences and humanities. Basque, Catalan, and Galician... all these languages are working in ParlaMint. I think we need more initiatives of its kind, providing an enriching environment for the development of tools, manuals, and university courses.”

Iruskieta mentioned additionally, that Poland is making significant progress in the field of language and humanities research, particularly through its involvement in CLARIN³². Poland has been actively engaged in developing and implementing interesting initiatives and services within the CLARIN infrastructure and has made notable contributions to CLARIN, potentially in terms of services, tools, or research projects.³³ It is the result of active participation and advancements of Polish researchers and institutions in the field of language and humanities research.

“There are a lot of services in CLARIN for Poland, more than for other countries. They have a very interesting view of what open science research is. Some of us in Spain look at European examples, but even more are looking at what is happening in South America. We maintain stronger connections with countries such as Mexico, Chile, and Argentina, rather than Europe. So, the interests are different.”

He explained that also the working cultures differ and developments must be obtained here as well:

“In Spain there is a strong interest in engaging in European projects, but the practice of working in an international context is not as prevalent. There is a need to embrace a multilingual perspective, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and navigate the process of transforming institutional working cultures, which is still in its early stages.”

Encouraging more institutions and researchers in Spain to join and actively contribute to initiatives in Spain present a challenge.

³¹ <https://www.clarin.eu/parlamint>

³² <https://clarin-pl.eu/index.php/en/about-us/>

³³ <https://clarin-pl.eu/index.php/en/alphabetical-list-of-services/>

NBIS (ELIXIR)

Background

The National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden (NBIS) is a national research infrastructure in the life sciences that serves as the bioinformatics platform at the Science for Life Laboratory (SciLifeLab). NBIS provides infrastructure and tools for bioinformatics analyses in order to facilitate these analyses for the users. It offers bioinformatics expertise in large-scale analysis of omics data, data integration, data management according to the FAIR data principles, data publishing for open science, systems development and artificial intelligence, imaging informatics, and advanced bioinformatics training. Uppsala University hosts NBIS.³⁴ NBIS is also the Swedish contact point to the European infrastructure for biological information ELIXIR. Interviews were conducted with a) Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström, responsible for data management, service design, integrations, repositories, CodeRefinery, Software Carpentry³⁵, and b) Niclas Jareborg, responsible for data management, agile project management, informatics, programming.

For better orientation, the following bullet points briefly summarize tasks and challenges that were mentioned in the interviews. They are subsequently presented in more detail in the sections below.

Overview Key Tasks

- Promoting the adoption of open science practices
- Collaborating on AAI infrastructure, discuss and recommend solutions for a shared AAI system
- Creating incentives for researchers to spend time on data documentation for better accessibility, both at the national and European level
- Work towards harmonizing standards and services to achieve interoperability
- Lowering barriers for data sharing

Overview Key Challenges

- Compatibility between EOSC and national infrastructures, adhering to standards and privacy requirements
- Simplifying the complexities of metadata and standards to facilitate understanding and adoption

³⁴ <https://www.uu.se/en/research/research-infrastructure/national-research-infrastructures-hosted-by-uppsala-university/national-bioinformatics-infrastructure-sweden-nbis/>

³⁵ <https://software-carpentry.org/>

- Developing user-friendly tools for consistent data entry and easy interpretation of file formats
- Achieving cross-domain interoperability and harmonizing metadata schemas
- Convincing researchers of the benefits of open science, FAIR data and metadata usage

Examples of Responsibilities and Challenges

EOSC

NBIS does not have a specific EOSC strategy but the organization is represented in EOSC-related discussions at Uppsala University and in three of the advisory groups of the EOSC Association, co-chairing two of them. NBIS also acts as the Swedish node of the European infrastructure ELIXIR and there is a strategy that has been released from ELIXIR that explains how ELIXIR ties into the EOSC ecosystem. The ELIXIR-EOSC strategy³⁶ includes an overview of the different platforms that are part of ELIXIR, for example resources they promote and provide or the interoperability platform. However, it does not provide all the details as it is based on an enormous ecosystem of standards and technical specifications. For each single project a significant amount of time is needed to delve into the relevant user needs, standards and specifications.

EOSC is important for ELIXIR as an organization because the alternative would be to go forward in an isolated way. However, it is not obvious what exact parts of the EOSC can be used on the local level. Therefore, the providers are still negotiating how they would like to onboard themselves into the European arena. EOSC and structures for identifying similar infrastructure across EU member states are certainly of relevance:

“If you have partners in international projects, you might not be able to use the national resources of one country for all the partners. Then it would be good to find similar solutions for the different members so that they can get similar infrastructures or benefit from possible cost recovery and even fit that into funding models”, Nyberg Åkerström explains.

Open Science

There is a push from the European level that research outputs should be shared as open as possible and at the same time as restricted as necessary. OS is very high on the NBIS agenda, and it is high on the EOSC agenda. NBIS has representatives in the different EOSC Association task forces that are converging on some recommendations and discuss solutions from different points of view. One of those is a shared authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI).

³⁶ ELIXIR EOSC Strategy 2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7120997>

“We also have the compute and storage part of NBIS, which is part of [the AAI] EOSC task force and contributing to the discussions. And on the Nordic level, we are doing collaborations which include interactions with the EOSC Nordic project. A lot of the things that we're working on, on the Nordic level, converge into the European context as well. Describing, for example, how to create incentives for researchers to spend time on preparing data and documentation to be published in a way that makes them accessible” (Nyberg Åkerström).

In Sweden, most universities now have research data policies and open access policies. There is an ELIXIR position paper on FAIR Data Management in the life sciences. Initiatives coordinated by ELIXIR are required to follow ELIXIR's policies and NBIS tries to actively promote solutions to adopt open science practices in all of its activities. But since all members and all national nodes of ELIXIR belong to one or more institutions, ELIXIR cannot impose on those members to adhere to anything that could conflict with the host institute's priorities.

“From NBIS side, we do have some recommendations, at least for making sure that data is publicly published. But as a national infrastructure, I think it would be difficult for us to keep track of all the different member institutes' policies. To some extent, we could say that if you want to use our services, then you need to accept these terms. But we don't want to discourage people from using our services or get the perception that it's going to cost them more time to use our services than it would give them for taking our help. And we don't need to push that hard ourselves for people to publish the data. The strongest push comes from the life science scientific journals by requiring that researchers publish the data to get articles accepted. We need to push for them to make better descriptions, documentation, use standards for metadata for the data and perhaps standards for the data files themselves to make the data FAIRer than it is today”, Jareborg explains.

Both, the EOSC ambition, to provide a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where users can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services, as well as open science policies or recommendations on the national level, provide the framework in which to work. But the feasibility of connecting infrastructures on a European level is also linked to challenges of the daily business within the home infrastructure. In the following examples, Jareborg and Nyberg Åkerström share observations that need to be taken into account when thinking about connecting infrastructures, interoperability and data sharing.

Interoperability

From the user's perspective the whole system needs to be simpler: a researcher might come with data and wants to use a different set of tools from the platform. The user should be able to choose anything from the processing tools through the computing resources up until the repositories or publishing services. Therefore, there must be an interoperability pattern. Currently, ELIXIR as an organization doesn't offer a service catalog that researchers can

address directly. But EOSC works towards a service catalogue that will over time become more comprehensive.

Interoperability and operational requirements on the EOSC side need to be easily compatible with existing infrastructure, standards and practices, including the work with human sensitive data that ask for special requirements regarding privacy. This is a challenge for NBIS because so far standards and services are not yet fully harmonized within the related research disciplines and clinical data spaces. This would certainly be a necessary prerequisite to ensure functioning interoperability later via the EOSC as well.

To achieve cross-scientific domain interoperability is also of value for ELIXIR:

“Harmonization then needs to be achieved on so many different levels, on so many different types of services, how to realize things technologically, how to get access to services, simple things like logging. For example, an authentication and authorization infrastructure being able to log in and to know who the person is, and to trust that identity... there are these kinds of technological solutions, a whole landscape. And we have some of those that might work across countries”, Jareborg comments.

There is an effort of making sure that there is a solution for the entire EOSC ecosystem and there are several login solutions in place that would grant you access to resources, “but what is the requirement from the countries that would be identifying a person and then relaying that information to other countries? Trust is needed on both ends”, Jareborg explains. The challenge currently being worked on is, not to redo all of the existing infrastructure in a country, but to find out the compatibilities and work on technical aspects, to make sure that information can flow between countries:

“There's quite a road ahead until we can say that we're really adopting EOSC—both in terms of defining the components and operational conditions for EOSC itself and converging on reliable implementations that work across regional and disciplinary borders”. (Nyberg Åkerström)

User-NBIS-Workflow

NBIS supports the Swedish research community to build knowledge by helping analyze large components of data. The focus of NBIS is on the data. Bioinformatics is the combination of computer science, statistics, and biology, basically. Most of the staff are active in giving research projects support and doing bioinformatics analysis. NBIS also engages in building infrastructures, for example a repository for sensitive human biomolecular data.

Regarding the workflow, research projects usually generate data, either in their own labs or by using the services of an infrastructure platform such as a sequencing core facility. If they contact NBIS at the beginning of the process, NBIS can help them design a statistically sound study. One problem often is that researchers may generate data without the appropriate

competence to design a statistically solid study. But even if the study is well designed, and a core facility offers some sort of standard analysis, they may still do not know how to really look for the answers they are after. A lot of research groups acknowledge that they could get more data and more answers when using new technologies, but they often do not have the knowledge or the capacity to do the bioinformatics analysis. Moreover, they often do not have the means to hire someone for that work.

And this is where NBIS comes in by providing bioinformatics analysis services for researchers.

“We also offer a lot of training activities around bioinformatics, training on postgraduate level and above about how to do certain types of analysis, how to learn a programming language to be able to do your analysis... And we have courses and training around how to manage data in a good way.” (Jareborg)

There is also a set of EU projects coordinated by ELIXIR.³⁷ Moreover, there are missing pieces of the infrastructure, for example for sensitive human data. NBIS is developing an archive for human related biomolecular research data as part of a larger federated network of similar repositories across Europe. NBIS is working with those repositories that are sustainable and of high quality, i.e. trustworthy. There is activity to get a network of interconnected data that adhere to good practice standards so that it could be interoperable with the tools within ELIXIR. In this manner, ELIXIR can be seen as a realization of the vision that EOSC seeks to attain.³⁸ This approach has now been adopted at the global level by the global level in the Global Biodata Coalition.³⁹

Analyzing and Standards

In bioinformatics, there are standards that people have taken for granted, for example data generated by sequencing facilities usually come in a standard format. It is to be recorded in a certain way, and contextual information should always be included. Without the contextual information, it is unclear how to further process the data. There are some file formats that are widely adopted and methods that are well tested and have been used for a very long time, that is those can more or less be considered as standards as well. A sequencing facility usually offers standard procedures, file formats and analyzing tools that are more or less like “press the button, get the result”.

But NBIS is working rather on method-developing. NBIS has experts in the domain of bioinformatics that develop new tools and adapt methods to do specific analysis that have not necessarily been done in this way before. With the variations of new research data, it is not

³⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9656.2>

³⁹ <https://globalbiodata.org/>

always obvious how to interpret information. Sometimes new things are discovered that need new descriptions and names. This is relevant because it is a lot of detailed work on how to find relevant statistics, on how pieces of data fit together, and on how to form a more abstract level of information that can even be interpreted by the scientists themselves. NBIS works at both ends of the spectrum at the same time.

There is still a need of people who work on data management to guide the researchers and show them what the standards are and how to connect to those:

“We try to promote good practices for describing datasets. When the researchers are recording a dataset, we propose that they look for already existing descriptions – not really standards, but at least a description with explanations of the parameters that shall be collected, and reference of that description somewhere, so that datasets could be merged in the future.” (Jareborg)

Lowering the Barriers for Data Sharing Solutions

If research funders or journals require to publish something, then the path to publishing should be as streamlined as possible. ELIXIR offers solutions to data sharing and a list of recommended repositories where researchers should deposit their data. There is a data platform, an interoperability platform, a tools platform, a training platform and a compute platform. These are different aspects of an ecosystem around bioinformatics and the research that relies on bioinformatics. Each of these platforms are identifying solutions that would be useful across all the member states and have recommendations for solutions that could be adopted and promoted.

It might not be possible to collect and send a biological sample across the world for many reasons. Therefore, researchers work with an abstract version of the sample that has been processed by different tools. It is necessary to precisely know how information is generated in an accurate manner.

Creating acceptance to use the available solutions as well as highlighting the future benefit of this is of importance for NBIS:

“We have a large community of people across the different countries that could contribute to improving these shared resources—making them easier to use and making sure that they interoperate and work well together. So, lowering the barrier could be to make sure that there is a truly interconnected ecosystem that can demonstrate the value of putting in the effort into making data conform to a certain standard. That is, putting in the effort would mean seamless access to a comprehensive set of relevant tools and services and it would be easier to publish the data in a data repository. (...) NBIS works across all areas of metadata and data interoperability to support researchers in adopting and realizing the value proposition of the FAIR data principles.” (Nyberg Åkerström)

He points out that the data sets, columns and so forth can be accurately and understandably described so that for example someone specialized in one discipline can search for and discover data that has been produced in another discipline. An example would be research on the COVID-19 and its impact that can include social sciences and the biomolecular aspects in the same project, looking at societal impact factors in connection to the spread of different variants and the impact on health care and symptoms in patients. Ideally, it would be nice to have more of those interconnected hubs of data where the user could find and connect data sets across disciplines.

Metadata-Challenge

One major challenge in the life sciences therefore is describing biological samples, which is linked to metadata, as Jareborg explains:

“If you want to do this properly, this is about ontologies and standards and few researchers are interested in this. But it's very important to fulfill the FAIR principles and especially machine-actionable FAIR. It is extremely important but researchers are not educated in this. A lot of them feel that it is too complicated.”

Finding the ways to make it easier for researchers, is the biggest challenge. So far there are no good tools for people to do standardized data entry, tools that help converge on required standards and connect the local attributes that researchers collect to some central repository of different versions. Ways of facilitating the process of developing data structures and converging those to the accepted standards of the larger research community are needed.

“We are interested in supporting convergence and adoption of shared metadata schemas and vocabularies. And, ideally, they would be produced and distributed using file formats that could be read and interpreted directly by tools and services in the ecosystem. The problem is that there are very few tools that can read these file formats, there are even fewer tools that can produce them, and there's a know-how barrier for people to be self-sufficient in working on this.” (Nyberg Åkerström).

A challenge and hard requirement to get wide adoption is that researchers to a larger degree can participate in this work themselves without having to rely on others producing the tools and asking them up-front for requirements. Researchers need to develop on and continuously curate these conventions as the knowledge and methods in their disciplines expand. And here a change of mindset plays a role, getting them to see the value of this work... being able to showcase and demonstrate this value, “I think, is also a high on the agenda for us to tackle”, Nyberg Åkerström says.

NBIS first approach would be to guide the researchers on how to do it and make it possible for them to do it on their own easily the next time. But they would go as far as to take the

data, the hard drive or whatever they have, and to steward the data from that hard drive to the repository on their behalf. And those are free services of NBIS.

To have all data well described in place will save the researchers time, especially when it comes to future projects linked to that data. Nyberg Åkerström and Jareborg observe that the younger researchers are more open to the benefits of Open Science and FAIR and to new technologies. Older research groups often think this is a waste of time. Success stories that are actually out there are about time not wasted but efficiently used.

Communication and encouragement are key here. With regard to involvement of users, it is necessary to a) communicate with the researchers what is available, repositories for example, b) encourage the researchers to use the tools and services, and c) offer to the researchers support and help.

Summary Main Challenges of Connecting and Integration

This chapter outlines recurring challenges that were mentioned in the interviews with regard to connecting DRIs. Furthermore, the three aspects workload, time, and creativity play a crucial role for all the challenges because they influence the processes and development when connecting DRIs.

Alignment of Goals and Priorities

To enhance connectivity within European DRIs mutually beneficial collaboration plans need to be developed and put in place. Finding common grounds for varying goals, priorities, and research agendas requires identifying shared research objectives, and to understand the strengths and expertise but also weak aspects of each infrastructure. A straight-forward coordination is necessary to determine the realistic goals, not only from the developers' point of view, but especially with regard to the needs of the users.

Cultural and Organizational Differences

DRIs have their own unique cultures, organizational structures, and decision-making processes depending on country, institution and discipline. It is necessary to align with different sets of values, norms, and working styles. Language barriers and differences in working cultures can lead to misunderstandings and slow processes down, despite pursuing the same goals. Additionally, complex infrastructures involve interdisciplinary research. Bridging the gaps between different disciplines, understanding and integrating diverse methodologies and approaches, is challenging due to differences in metadata-organization, terminologies, and research habits.

Governance and Decision-Making

DRIs typically have governance structures in place to manage their operations and decision-making processes. Joining another infrastructure involves negotiating new governance arrangements, including representation, decision-making authority, and resource allocation. Balancing the interests and priorities of different stakeholders within the larger infrastructure is difficult, especially when keeping the specific user's needs in mind – that also might differ from country to country, as well as from discipline to discipline.

Integration of Systems and Processes

Connecting DRIs requires the integration of systems, processes, and protocols. This is challenging because the infrastructures have different technological platforms, data management systems, and operational procedures – and users have different expectations with regard to the services before and even more so, after connecting. Harmonizing these elements and ensuring a smooth transition is very time-consuming, complex and requires a lot of workloads for the developers and all working staff involved. A failed integration of services results in the problem that users cannot reach the information and data they need.

Intellectual Property and Data Sharing

Sharing data among DRIs is crucial for collaboration and scientific progress. Intellectual property rights and data sharing policies vary between DRIs and concerns about data privacy, security, and intellectual property rights pose challenges. Developing agreements, and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations are part of the connecting processes and may even hinder the progress due to slow processes or because of not finding a common ground.

Technical Compatibility

Achieving technical compatibility that should enable full integration of the different DRIs is challenging because it requires well-built infrastructures establishing common standards, and data exchange mechanisms ensuring effective communication and interoperability. This can conflict with specific technical requirements that were built with regard to the necessities of local projects. To integrate the registered technical infrastructures necessarily leads to complexity that also has to be managed.

Workload, Time and Creativity

Connecting DRIs is about connecting growing and changing structures, while maintaining their stable functions and quality – and at the same time with the goal of opening new opportunities for science. Ideally, this should benefit the researchers. Integrating the a complex DRI (and encompassing its evolving technical, linguistic, cultural, and political aspects) with an even

more complex DRI for example on a European level, demands a substantial investment of workload, time, and creativity.

Personnel Workload

All the interviews showed that connecting DRIs is a collaborative effort involving the contribution of multiple individuals, teams, and stakeholders. The individual workload is substantial and is related to various domains, including technical, legal, and financial project management, communication, but also protecting research habits and enabling standards on a superordinate level of the connected infrastructures. Long processes and yet often little or even no progress are also part of the workload, as they are perceived as burdensome.

- a) Planning the connection of DRIs includes identifying the infrastructures to be connected, defining objectives and scope, assessing compatibility, and establishing communication channels. Coordinating the efforts of multiple teams involved requires careful planning and coordination which leads to a lot of meetings.
- b) The technical implementation of connecting DRIs requires a large workload for ensuring compatibility, for integrating systems and technologies, for developing data sharing protocols, and for addressing and solving interoperability difficulties.
- c) Defining and establishing governance structures and decision-making processes for the (to be) connected infrastructures, such as developing agreements, protocols and policies implies a substantial workload. Legal experts, policymakers, and stakeholders contribute to shaping the governance framework, numerous coordination in meetings and the development of common documents is necessary.
- d) Managing resources for the connected DRIs involves allocating funding, personnel, and equipment to support the connection. The identification of all necessary management and technical processes both in the original infrastructure and in the resulting connected infrastructure requires efforts.
- e) Addressing legal aspects such as ensuring compliance with data protection regulations, intellectual property rights, ethics guidelines, and relevant national and international laws involve high workload. Legal experts and compliance officers contribute to navigating these legal and regulatory complexities.
- f) Providing training and setting up capacity building initiatives to enhance the skills and knowledge required for connecting services also require efforts: organizing workshops, training sessions, and knowledge transfer support via online sources, etc.
- g) Psychological workload results from the cognitive demands for all people involved. Creating acceptance to use newly available solutions as well as highlighting the future benefits of these services is of importance and it implies lowering the user-barrier by

making sure that there is a trusted, truly interconnected ecosystem. Therefore close communication about good and challenging experiences, needs and ideas is necessary.

Time

Impatience sets in on all sides when expectations are high, for example when the benefits of connected DRIs based on European infrastructures are advertised, but this goal is not immediately visible since related processes need more time to be fully realised.

Examples of such time-consuming aspects are:

- the planning and implementation phases, coordination of efforts, and definition of objectives for technical integration, development of protocols, definition and establishment of governance structures, discussion of legal and regulatory aspects, decision making, obtaining approvals, reaching consensus, aligning priorities. Weekly meetings over months and years are needed. Modifying decisions, such as after receiving a report, requires implementing new changes and adjusting ongoing processes.
- addressing technical compatibility, data formats, interoperability, and software integration and testing, negotiating solutions.
- assessing available resources, allocating resources for personnel and equipment, securing additional funding if necessary.
- learning, training and capacity building activities for workshops, training sessions and knowledge transfer activities so that users of the services, tools etc. or those who are connecting them can gain the necessary expertise. Test if all this makes sense, change or improve if necessary.
- knowledge exchange among the connected infrastructures. Regular meetings, joint projects, production and sharing of research outcomes and findings, as well as creating platforms and opportunities for knowledge sharing and public visibility. The production of reports, stories and other output to demonstrate and promote the benefits of collaborative research through connected infrastructures.
- Pressure due to lack of time often leads individuals to prioritize activities that are more predictable and controllable over creative actions.

Creativity

High workload and limited time during the connection processes suppress creativity and hinder innovative thinking. But connecting DRIs involves addressing various challenges, such as technical compatibility, data integration, as well as cultural and linguistic barriers.

Creative thinking however is essential for generating solutions:

- Integrating different DRIs often requires finding ways to make diverse systems, technologies, and data formats work together. Creative problem-solving is necessary to bridge gaps, identify common standards, and develop solutions that ensure interoperability and compatibility between the infrastructures. It also helps in developing innovative communication channels, platforms, and tools to facilitate information exchange and collaboration between the teams involved.
- Connecting DRIs opens up new possibilities for interdisciplinary collaborations, joint research projects, and access to new resources and expertise. Creativity is crucial for identifying and exploring new research opportunities and how the services and tools of the connected infrastructures can help solving complex or new questions.
- Fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation within the connected infrastructures relies on creative thinking. Identifying opportunities for optimization, refining processes, and adapting to new observations, needs and technologies. Creative problem-solving allows for learning from experiences and for improving the connecting processes.

Reflecting on Connecting DRIs

DRIs have specific user-oriented structures and functions. The EOSC vision is to create a user-friendly interoperability that takes research and science to a new level. Alliances like ENLIGHT would like to benefit from connected DRIs. There are many ideas for realizing this vision. The infrastructure providers with their experience and knowledge contribute to this realization as well as the users who would like to see their wishes and requirements met. To fulfill this vision, theory and practice must be brought together. Well-developed large DRIs and less developed smaller DRIs are a current result of numerous processes in which technical and organizational tasks have been implemented. However, these have to be kept functional for the user, and at the same time they need to be enriched with the growing domain-specific content. This alone is a major task. As the connection at the level of European DRIs presents an additional task, it is necessary to decide what added value the integration should generate.

At the initial stage, an examination of the individual steps is needed for the practical realization; furthermore, it must be evaluated if the expected goals are met, both on a technical and user level. One way to approach this challenge is to be open to developments that allow the achievement and testing of many small goals – which eventually lead to the realization of the “grand vision”. It is crucial to bear in mind that the perspective and priorities of individuals involved in the integration process may shift away from aligning with the user needs and requirements, owing to the demands imposed by their detailed work. The user, typically an impatient and demanding researcher under time constraints, needs a simple, clear,

smoothly functioning system that can be utilized without substantial extra effort and without barriers. To convince users that the connection of DRIs at the European level is beneficial to their research, these users must have access to success stories when working with those infrastructures. The vision of what connected DRIs should offer then may shift, however, sometimes there remains a gap between what is aimed for as a vision and the actual user experience. Therefore – and this may sound trivial or may have been stated many times before – establishing a close and continuous understanding and negotiation between developers and users is and remains crucial in DRI integration processes.

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Appendix

1. Table Full Code System Sorted by Frequency

Code	Frequency (all interviews)
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service	410
data	287
infrastructure	244
researcher and research	198
EOSC	191
Integration	134
resource	132
core service	131
Provider	115
onboarding	104
interoperability	103
science	94
user, mindset change	90
connect	69
technic	57
benefit	53
standards	48
portal	47
software	45
future	44
EU	43
Institution	42
access	41
Open Science	40
support users	39
difficult	29
training	25
solutions	22
policy	21
challenges	20
Open Access	15
FAIR	15
critics	14
interconnect	13
strategy	11
network	10
implementation	7
account	6

recommendations	3
TRL	3
lessons learned	1

2. Questions of the Semi-Structured Interviews

In all of the interviews a conversation started with questions from the list below. Other questions were then integrated into the conversation depending on how the topics developed.

- What was their journey to so far for the integration? What were their goals and which steps were conducted in order to achieve these goals?
- Does the integration in European infrastructure influence the services on national level (new/other services offered, optimization of services)?
- Does the location of the national DRI matter when connecting to another one? (What infrastructures can they already rely on so that integrating into new/different ones might be easier/more difficult?)
- Do the existing services of the institution matter for the integration?
- What is the nature and the context of the integration process?
- What lessons have been learned so far when integrating/trying to integrate
- Where do the partner universities invest in, how does the investment for the integration shape/influence the process?
- How are the infrastructures maintained, permanent commitment?
- What are suggestions for improvement, where are needs for support (storage, archiving, legal support...?)
- Are there challenges and gaps for compliance with EOSC rules of participation, guidance for onboarding service providers, responsibilities after registration of services?
- How does/could the integration into European infrastructures complement and enhance provided services
- What is the integration step by step workflow? Who is informing whom about what and who "is doing the job"?
- How much time and workload are required and mostly what for?
- How does integration differ with regard to the providers? Is there something like the onboarding tutorial, an integration tutorial?
- What has so far been integrated into which Core Services (or others?) and how did that go, what went well, what not and why?
- What preconditions must be met by those who are providing RI and how is this communicated?
- What actions are being taken when the provider does not fully meet the requirements?
- What happens, when the EOSC infrastructure is not sufficiently well developed to meet the requirements of the providers' services?